

Cost estimation in the context of Manufacturing-as-a-Service

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Abstract: Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) represents a transformative shift in industrial production, offering flexible and scalable solutions through the use of shared manufacturing resources. However, the on-demand and variable nature of MaaS poses significant challenges in accurately estimating costs. This paper addresses these challenges by reviewing existing costing methods and selecting Activity-Based Costing (ABC) as the most suitable approach. A framework for cost estimation in this context is then proposed, followed by the use of simulation to support the implementation of ABC. The feasibility of this approach is demonstrated in a smart factory environment, showcasing how simulation can enhance cost estimation in a controlled setting. Finally, the methodology is examined from an industrial perspective, highlighting potential challenges and considerations for real-world application.

Keywords: Manufacturing-as-a-service, Modeling and simulation, Digital enterprise, Costing, Activity-based costing

1. INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) is a paradigm that departs from traditional manufacturing models, offering scalability and flexibility (Goldhar and Jelinek 1990) by enabling manufacturers to dynamically adjust their operations to accommodate on-demand and fluctuating customer needs. This evolution positions MaaS as a specific instance of Product-Service Systems (PSS), where manufacturing is provided as a service rather than as a standalone product enabling customers to outsource specific or entire processes on a temporary basis as a service (Annarelli, Battistella, and Nonino 2016). PSS business models integrate products and services to deliver value to customers. (Datta and Roy 2010) categorized existing PSS types and their associated costing models, which situates MaaS within the result-oriented PSS class. In this category, companies focus on delivering outcomes rather than selling physical products. In the context of MaaS, production is outsourced to service providers who offer manufacturing capabilities on demand. This aligns with PSS principles, by shifting the focus from owning manufacturing assets to accessing manufacturing services. Here, the “product” is the manufacturing capability itself, while the “services” encompass managing production, ensuring quality, and potentially handling logistics.

Accurate cost estimation, encompassing both products and services, is pivotal in MaaS as it directly influences pricing strategies and decision-making. However, the on-demand and fluctuating nature of MaaS introduces significant challenges. For instance, these challenges can be related to demand uncertainty which can complicate capacity planning for service providers, making it difficult to predict resource utilization. Cost allocation becomes particularly challenging in MaaS context due to shared resources spanning multiple customers and processes. Also, the lack of unified approach to costing across companies adds complexity, as MaaS often requires collaboration between different companies with different cost structures. Finally, while traditional manufacturing base cost estimates on existing products or projects, this approach may not be suitable in MaaS, where new unfamiliar products or services are requested by customers. These challenges underscore the limitation of conventional costing methods and highlights the need for adaptable approaches capable of addressing the nature of MaaS ecosystem.

Activity-based costing offers a promising solution for cost estimation in MaaS, allocating costs based on actual resource usage and activities (Gupta and Galloway 2003). To explore this potential, a proof of concept is applied to a simplified use case in a controlled environment, leveraging simulation to dynamically model activities and resources. Building on these insights, the study extends the methodology to a real-world industrial case, assessing its feasibility and applicability. This progression highlights the challenges and opportunities of cost estimation in an industrial MaaS setting, laying the groundwork for future advancements in the field.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the existing costing methods and discusses the selection of the most appropriate method for MaaS. Section 3 presents the proposed MaaS costing framework. Section 4 details the case study. Section 5 provides the discussion, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. REVIEW OF COST ESTIMATION APPROACHES AND METHOD SELECTION FOR MAAS

This section aims to review the existing cost estimation methods discussed in the literature and identify the most suitable approach for application in the MaaS context and its application in the literature.

Existing costing methods

Various review works on costing methods have been reported in the literature. One of the most widely recognized classifications of cost estimation techniques is the hierarchical framework proposed (Niazi et al. 2006). Other reviews have also examined costing methods from different perspectives, such as those focused on additive manufacturing product development (Kadir, Yusof, and Wahab 2020), aerospace composite manufacturing (Hueber, Horejsi, and Schledjewski 2016) while others focused on PSS cost estimation process (Rodríguez et al. 2020) or the adoption of product cost estimation methods to services (Huang, Newnes, and Parry 2012). All these reviews enable a broad categorization of cost estimation methods as follows: intuitive, analogical, parametric and analytical approaches. Intuitive methods rely solely on expert judgments using knowledge from past experiences to provide estimates, making them suitable for small scale, low-complexity scenarios. Analogical methods assume that similar products could have comparable costs, this method relies on analyzing data from past projects to estimate the current project's cost. Methods like regression are often used. Parametric methods, while systematic, rely on historical data and use statistical models to establish relationships between product costs and cost drivers, mathematically correlating these factors to estimate costs. Analytical methods involve calculating the total product cost by summing up the costs of all process steps. This method requires a detailed understanding of the processes and their interactions. It can be applied at various levels, including activities, operations, or specific features. In each case, the costs of individual elements at different levels are determined and then aggregated to derive the overall product cost.

Each method of estimation offers specific advantages and drawbacks depending on the level of detail required, the availability of information, and the stage of the project. Intuitive methods are quick but rely heavily on expertise, making them less reliable for complex or new tasks. Analogical methods use prior data, making them more efficient at the early stages of new projects when limited data are available, but may lack accuracy if projects differ significantly. Parametric methods are balanced using mathematical models to generate relationships based on specific parameters, providing greater accuracy, but requires reliable historical data as well as a deep understanding of the cost drivers and how they influence the overall product cost. Analytical methods, while time-intensive, are the most accurate, because they calculate costs at the granular level with error rates of 5-15% compared to 30-50% for other methods. According to (Luki, Milošević, and Borojevi 2016). they are detail-oriented, making it ideally suited for later phases or new products with detailed designs.

Considering all these factors, analytical methods emerge as the most adaptable and suitable approach for cost estimation in the MaaS context.

Activity-based costing

Among analytical methods, one of the widely adopted approaches is Activity-based costing (ABC) which further refines analytical methods by assigning costs to activities based on the resources they consume. This makes it a natural fit for MaaS, where dynamic, resource-sharing environments demand high granularity in cost allocation. This allows companies to allocate both direct and indirect costs more accurately by identifying which activities consume the most resources. The ABC process begins with identifying resources (e.g., machines, labor, energy) and their associated costs (Lee and Kao 2001). Resource drivers, such as machine usage hours or labor hours, are then used to distribute these costs across key activities, such as assembly, inspection, or packaging. Next, activity drivers—such as the number of units processed, storage duration, or number of setups—link the costs of activities to specific cost objects such as products or customer orders. This approach ensures that the costs reflect actual resource usage (Mahal and Hossain 2015).

In contrast, traditional costing methods, such as volume-based costing, assign overhead costs to products or services based on a single cost driver, typically production volume. These methods often oversimplify cost allocation, leading to inaccuracies in complex environments (Jeyaraj 2015). ABC, on the other hand, tracks resource consumption at the activity level, ensuring precise cost distribution, even in scenarios with shared resources or

fluctuating demand. For example, while traditional methods may allocate overheads uniformly across all orders, ABC assigns costs based on actual usage, providing actionable insights for decision-making in MaaS.

The ABC method has been discussed in the literature, with several studies showcasing its benefits and highlighting challenges that may arise from its implementation. For instance, the paper (Somapa, Cools, and Dullaert 2012) explores the development of an ABC model within a small-sized road transport and logistics company. It highlights the method's potential to enhance cost estimation accuracy by using simplified parameters, making it particularly suitable for small firms. However, challenges such as the lack of quantitative data on cost drivers and the need for improved recording systems are noted, emphasizing the importance of system redesign to fully leverage method's benefits. The study (Schulze, Seuring, and Ewering 2012) addresses the limitations of traditional intra-firm cost accounting in supply chain management due to the absence of standardized cost definitions. It develops a conceptual framework for ABC in an inter-firm context, allowing for better cost exchange and comparison among supply chain members.

While ABC provides a more accurate and granular method of cost allocation, its implementation in complex and dynamic environments, such as MaaS, requires additional support. Here, simulation plays a pivotal role in refining ABC by modeling processes and resource consumption. It becomes possible to visualize and test cost allocation strategies in a virtual environment before applying them to actual operations by using simulation. Building on these insights, the following section explores how the integration of ABC with simulation has been studied.

Activity-based costing and simulation

ABC has been effectively integrated with simulation techniques across various domains to enhance cost estimation accuracy and address traditional costing limitations.

One study (Lee and Kao 2001) applied ABC with simulation to analyze operational costs in the Pu-Shin wholesale fish market, achieving more precise resource cost allocation and offering actionable cost management insights for agricultural systems. Another study (Özbayrak, Akgün, and Türker 2004) combined ABC with mathematical and simulation models to estimate manufacturing costs under Material Requirements Planning (MRP) and Just-In-Time (JIT) strategies, emphasizing their financial impacts. A third study (Kostakis et al. 2008) introduced a methodology combining ABC, simulation modeling, and data mining to improve cost driver definition, showcasing its application in healthcare for empirical cost estimation.

These examples underscore the effectiveness of integrating ABC with simulation to enhance cost estimation. However, it is noteworthy that much of the literature on this topic is dated, with limited recent advancements or applications reported. Leveraging these insights, this paper proposes a framework for cost estimation tailored to the MaaS context and introduces a proof of concept integrating simulation to support the implementation in a controlled environment.

3. MAAS COSTING FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 illustrates the framework of a cost estimation in a MaaS context, showcasing the interaction between the service providers and service consumers, and emphasizing the process of cost estimation. The process begins on the left with the service provider (a), who offers a portfolio of services, including details on capabilities, resource requirements, capacity, customization options, cost structures, and pricing. The service consumer (b), on the right, submits service requirements, including technical details and process parameters, for specific products or orders. The interaction begins with the consumer providing order details—such as quantities and delivery time, through the MaaS interface (c). The interface facilitates matching (e) by assessing the feasibility of the requested tasks (d). This step involves estimating costs (in this case, using ABC method) and comparing the existing resources and their availability against the requirements of the requested tasks. If the resources and tasks are compatible, the process proceeds to the next phase; otherwise, adjustments or alternative solutions are considered. Following this, the manufacturing process is initiated (f), with resources (e.g., machines, labor, energy) allocated to different activities based on defined drivers (e.g., machine usage hours). During the process, the service provider continuously monitors operations (g) to ensure compliance with the order specifications. ABC estimation is embedded within the process, breaking down resource consumption into activities and assigning those costs to cost objects (e.g., products or services) using activity drivers like units processed or storage duration. In the context of MaaS, it is essential to automate this cost estimation process through its integration in Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) or Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) to capture automatically and in real-time resource usage and activity-related data and reduce error margin. Once production is completed, the product or service is delivered to the service consumer (h), accompanied by the finalized price. A feedback loop is incorporated (i), allowing consumers to provide input, such as evaluation of service quality, adherence to delivery timeline or deviation from initial pricing. This would help refine service offerings and improve the cost estimation process for future orders.

Figure 1. Cost estimation framework for MaaS

4.

PROOF OF CONCEPT

This section presents the proof of concept, which aims to demonstrate the feasibility of the ABC approach using simulation in a dynamic MaaS environment. While the proof of concept may appear straightforward, it serves to identify potential challenges and opportunities within the context of MaaS.

Smart factory description

The smart factory operates with two parallel production lines, as depicted in Figure 2 and further detailed in the schematic representation in Figure 3. On the first line, the process begins at a manually fed storage area (0). When an order is launched via the Manufacturing Execution System (MES), an automated storage system (1) retrieves a pallet equipped with an RFID tag containing the fabrication order and delivers it to a laser inspection station (2). Pallets with correct dimensions proceed to production, while defective ones are returned to storage. A pick-and-place robot (3) transfers the pallet to a workstation, retrieves PCBs from a nearby storage bin, and assembles fuses according to the production order. The PCB storage is replenished by an automated guided vehicle (AGV) from the automated storage and retrieval system (AS/RS). After assembly, the AGV transports the pallet to the second production line (4). On the second line, an operator verifies the placement of components (5). A camera inspection system then checks the pallet against the production order (6). If approved, a dispenser places the top cover (7), which is pressed into place at the next station (8). The AGV then returns the pallet to the first line for labeling (9). Finally, the operator prepares the pallet for transport back to the AS/RS (10). Further details about the line are in the study (Cunha et al. 2021).

In the MaaS context, activities are the foundational elements of service delivery, defined by the tasks or processes needed to fulfill customer orders. They are identified by analyzing the production workflow to break it into discrete steps (e.g., storing, transporting, assembling), categorizing activities into value-adding tasks (e.g., assembly, inspection) and others, and mapping them to customer-specific orders. The colors in Figure 3 highlight the identified groups of activities and are broken down further later.

Figure 2. Smart factory

Figure 3. Smart factory process

Simulation flowchart

Figure 4 illustrates the flow of information and processes across three main components: inputs, the simulation model, and outputs, with a feedback loop for iterative improvements. Inputs include all the data required to set up and execute the simulation, such as customer orders, which detail the orders placed by customers; process specifications, which represent the operational details and routing of manufacturing processes; cost driver rates, which are the rates assigned to various cost drivers, linking resource usage to specific activities; and scenario-related inputs, which define the parameters and conditions specific to the scenario being simulated, such as demand variability and production constraints.

At the core of the framework, the simulation model integrates the input data and executes processes to achieve several functions. These include process execution, which simulates the manufacturing process based on the defined specifications and orders; resource usage tracking, which monitors the utilization of resources during the simulation; cost allocation, which assigns costs to activities and orders based on resource usage and cost driver rates; and scenario evaluation, which assesses the impact of specific conditions on performance metrics and cost efficiency.

The outputs generated by the simulation model are categorized into measurable outcomes. These include orders cost driver volumes, which represent the total resource usage (cost driver volumes) attributable to each customer order; resource utilization rates, which measure how effectively resources are employed; order-specific estimated costs, which are the calculated costs associated with fulfilling each customer order; and scenario-specific metrics, which are performance indicators relevant to the simulated scenario, such as lead time or production efficiency.

Finally, the feedback loop enables the refinement of inputs and scenarios based on the outputs, facilitating iterative improvement in cost estimation and resource management.

Application of simulation to ABC

Simulation is used to model the smart factory instead of directly relying on the real system for several reasons. First, it provides a controlled environment to test and validate the implementation of the ABC method without disrupting actual operations. Second, it offers the flexibility to explore various scenarios, such as adjustments in production volume, resource allocation, or activity sequencing.

Figure 4. Simulation model flowchart

For this purpose, FlexSim simulation software is used as a tool. The simulation model is developed by observing and analyzing the actual processing times for various activities. It is known that the processing time for the workstations. To introduce stochastic behavior and enhance realism, a normal distribution with a defined mean and variance is assumed. This accounts for potential variability caused by minor disruptions or differences in operation. For the robot, variability is introduced in its movement times, while for task executors such as operators and AGVs, stochastic behavior is incorporated into their load and unload times. This approach ensures a more dynamic and realistic representation of the system. The resulting simulation model is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Smart factory simulation model

The activities identified in the smart factory are categorized based on resource usage. Table 1 summarizes the activities, operations, associated resources, cost categories, and potential resource drivers. Simulation estimates the resource driver volumes. These results, combined with resource costs, enable the computation of resource costs for each activity and the activity cost driver rates. Activity costs are allocated to cost objects (e.g., customer orders) based on activity cost drivers. Each customer order is associated with a manufacturing routing and incurs resource usage aligned with the defined activities.

Resource costs are linked to the activities they support and are identified and collected by considering the resources required for each activity. Machine costs, include depreciation, maintenance, and operational expenses (e.g., electricity). Labor costs are based on wages, working hours, and activity duration, monitored via MES or time-logging systems. Material costs are determined by consumption rates of raw materials and consumables, tracked through ERP or inventory systems. Overhead costs, such as utilities or factory space, are allocated proportionally using resource drivers like machine runtime, labor hours, or material consumption. These costs are distributed based on how resources are consumed in each activity.

Table 1. Activity classification, resources and cost driver's identification

Activity	Operation	Resource	Resource costs	Cost drivers
Storing	Storing and feeding pallets and back covers	AS/RS 1	Cost of electricity, storage cost	Stored item per unit of time
	Storing final products	AS/RS 2		
Transporting	Transporting pallets	AGV 1	Cost of electricity	Total travel distance and number of transported items
	Transporting pallets	AGV 2		
Inspecting	Dimensional inspection	Laser	Cost of electricity	Number of processed items, inspection time
	Visual inspection	Camera		
Mounting	Mounting PCBs and inserting fuses	Robot	Cost of electricity, cost of consumables,	Number of movements, number per products
Assembling	Mounting top cover	Machine 1	Cost of electricity	Number of processed items, cycle time
	Pressing top cover	Machine 2		
	Labeling	Machine 3		
Manual tasks	Mounting back covers on pallets	Operator 1	Staff wages	Number of handled items
	Pick and place final products	Operator 2		
	Manual inspection	Operator 3		

5. DISCUSSION

While the proof of concept is hypothetical and simulated, applying this framework in real-world scenarios requires a collaborative, systematic approach to overcome the inherent challenges. In practical scenarios, resource costs are typically obtained from various sources, such as internal financial records or ERP systems that track operating costs, as well as historical data on resource usage, energy consumption, and staff wages. However, ensuring accuracy, consistency, and completeness in data collection from different sources can be challenging, as it requires integration in a consistent format. In the MaaS context, frequent changes in customer orders, custom production processes, and differing resource usage make it hard to standardize data collection.

Determining how to allocate limited capacity (e.g., machine availability, labor hours) across multiple customer orders can be complex, especially when demand fluctuates. Customers may place last-minute orders or request changes, leading to unanticipated capacity constraints and cost overruns.

In MaaS, resources are often shared across multiple customer orders and services. Allocating these indirect costs fairly and accurately to individual customers or activities requires robust tracking and clear attribution mechanisms, which can be challenging due to the variability in service usage.

For new or customized services offered within a MaaS framework, historical data on resource usage or costs may be insufficient or nonexistent. This makes it difficult to establish reliable cost drivers and validate the calculated rates.

Lastly, although analytical models demonstrate the lowest cost estimation error, activity-based costing methods also require substantial resources to implement (Abdul Majid and Sulaiman 2008) potentially requiring new software, training, and changes to existing processes.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper explored cost estimation within the context of MaaS. The ABC method, with its focus on accurately assigning costs to activities based on resource consumption, provides a detailed approach to cost estimation that is particularly suited for dynamic, resource-sharing environments like MaaS. Through simulation, it is possible to test and refine cost allocation strategies in a virtual environment before applying them to real-world operations. The challenges identified in the literature, such as data collection issues and the complexity of accurately allocating costs in dynamic environments, are particularly relevant in the MaaS context. Moving forward, further research could focus on refining the integration of ABC in real-world MaaS scenarios, addressing additional complexities like real-time data integration and scalability, which will be crucial for its broader adoption across industries.

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